

D3.1 Guidelines to update and upgrade the Catalogue

Grant Agreement Number	825640
Project Acronym	DIHNET.EU
Deliverable Date	April 2019
Authors	Begoña Sanchez (TECNALIA)
Number of Pages	24
Number of Annexes	1
Version	1.0
Reviewed by	The Consortium
Approved by	The Consortium
Dissemination level	Public

The overall aim of DIHNET.EU is to create a sustainable European network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), by developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different DIH networks, DIHs and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The project will act as a coordinator to enhance the collaboration, aligning and synchronizing their activities. This is considered crucial for a better support of SMEs and MidCap companies in offering and using digitisation services.

The project is carried out by TNO, TECNALIA, Fundingbox, euRobotics, BluMorpho and FEDIL, have strong experience in DIHs and well connected to the EU DIH community.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 825640.
www.dihnet.eu

Executive Summary

DIHNET.EU aims to create a sustainable European network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), by developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different DIH networks, DIHs and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe.

This document presents a **vision for the upgrade and update of the Catalogue**, with a special focus on the need to boost collaboration among DIHs and networking towards a pan-European network of DIHs. The Catalogue is a platform that offers opportunities for cooperation and communication on expertise to potential customers by showcasing their services at European level, etc. The availability of information on 'who-is-who' creates opportunities to find possible cooperation's between the DIHs and stimulate a pan-European network. Therefore, the Catalogue needs to provide updated and useful information for the potential customers and users.

Deliverable 3.1: Guidelines to update the Catalogue is framed under **WP3: Upgrade of the Catalogue; Task 3.1: Updating and upgrading the Catalogue**, led by Tecnalía. **Deliverable 3.1** aims to provide Guidelines to upgrade the Catalogue, including a structured approach to collect and assess information for the Catalogue, in close cooperation with the other DIH agents, DIHs and other stakeholders. This will permit to increase the quality of the information provided to SMEs, mid-caps, entrepreneurs and other stakeholders.

Chapter 1 present the scope of the Deliverable and how this is framed under DIHNET.EU. **Chapter 2** describes the History of the Catalogue and related initiatives. **Chapter 3** shows the Purpose of the Catalogue, the main potential users as well as a SWOT analysis. **Chapter 4** presents the DIHNET.EU approach to upgrade the Catalogue and **Chapter 5** the Top-ten Guidelines to upgrade the Catalogue. In **Annex 1**, we suggest some questions to get additional information for the upgrade of the Catalogue. In Annex2, the Guidelines developed to support DIHs while filling in the information requested by JRC before being published in the Catalogue.

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1 Introduction

1.1 About DIHNET.EU

The overall aim of DIHNET.EU is to create a sustainable European network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), by developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different DIH networks, DIHs and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The project will act as a coordinator to enhance the collaboration, aligning and synchronizing their activities. This is considered crucial for a better support of SMEs and MidCap companies in offering and using digitisation services.

The project is coordinated by TNO and implemented together with Tecnalía, Fundingbox, euRobotics, BluMorpho and FEDIL, partners with strong experience on the field.

This deliverable provides Guidelines for the update and upgrade the Catalogue, aiming at enhancing the collaboration and cooperation of DIHs, key to reach the overall aim of DIHNET.EU.

1.2 Context of Deliverable 3.1

Deliverable 3.1: Guidelines to update the Catalogue is framed under **WP3: Upgrade of the Catalogue; Task 3.1: Updating and upgrading the Catalogue**, led by Tecnalía and with contributions from TNO. It is expected that this activity will last from M1 to M6.

WP3 aims to **upgrade the Catalogue** of DIHs by **identifying, supporting and reinforcing the collaboration activities and capacities of the DIHs**. Therefore, to support the creation of a sustainable network of specialised DIHs. Based on the Catalogue, the individual DIHs will better network and create a dynamic European DIH Community. The specific objectives of WP3 are:

- To provide a common framework for the upgrade and update of the information provided by the Catalogue, by defining a structured approach to collect and update information from DIHs.
- To initiate the actual upgrade of the Catalogue in cooperation with other DIH agents and individual DIHs.
- To create an overview of the European DIH landscape that can be fed into the further collaboration activities.
- To suggest Working Groups to make the EU DIH Community active (feeding in WP1).
- To provide a common approach for DIH Maturity Assessment leading to improved learning and exchange of experiences.

WP3 will impact and be developed specially in connection to WP1, WP2 and WP4.

Task 3.1: Updating and upgrading the Catalogue intends to update and upgrade the information provided by the Catalogue. The Catalogue has been created as part of the implementation of the DEI Strategy and contains information for any SME or industry on the existing competences to digitalise products and services. It has permitted to identify more than 500 DIHs and related initiatives in the EU, which have been classified under different criteria (e.g. country, evolutionary stages, technical

competencies, services provided, TRL, market sectors). The JRC¹ is working on the online tool to visualise the DIHs and their competencies.

The following chart shows how this deliverable is framed within the DIHNET.EU project:

1.3 Objectives of Deliverable 3.1

Deliverable 3.1 aims to provide **Guidelines to upgrade the Catalogue**, including a **structured approach to collect and assess information for the Catalogue**, in close cooperation with the other DIH agents, DIHs and other stakeholders. This will permit to increase the quality of the information provided to SMEs, mid-caps, entrepreneurs and other stakeholders.

1.4 Measurable Impact of Deliverable 3.1

As already indicated, the Catalogue is key for the success of the project impact, so although it will be impacting other activities, it will directly impact Objective 3 of the proposal:

- *Objective 3: To develop a clear overview of the DIH related services provided in Europe to better align the offering of services and improve access to the services offered, by providing a common framework for the upgrade and update of the information provided by the Catalogue of DIHs. The DIH Catalogue will be further improved in cooperation with the JRC and other networks. The project will facilitate the development of a structured approach, creating added value for all participants, but aligning their actions through a systematic multi-user data model (e.g. policymakers, SMEs/MidCaps, regional development agencies, individual DIHs, H2020 Innovation Actions, H2020 CSAs).*

More in detail also, the following KPIs measure performance.

¹ <http://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/digital-innovation-hubs-tool?>

KPI nº	KPI name	KPI target	Success
KPI 3.1.	Common framework defined	1 Guidelines defined	Reached in April M6
KPI 3.2	# of contacts with Cooperation with JRC and other networks to update Catalogue	At least 2 per year	Reached, as fluent contact exists for developments
KPI 3.3.	# of forms to better understand the demand and offer hosted at the platform and filled in by DIHs	1 form filled in by 50% of the DIHs from the Catalogue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Form will be available for Working Groups • Space available in the Community to understand concerns from DIHs

Milestones associated: MS1 Guidelines to update and upgrade the Catalogue (M6);

- *Objective 2 will be also impacted: Offering the DIHs an on-line infrastructure to support their collaboration. This platform will support the DIHNET.EU Community with a wide range of services, information and tools with different functionalities, that will help DIHs to communicate, align, collaborate and synchronise their way of thinking and action. It will include a training program and a set of impact analytics tools. It will also allow regional entities to create a specialised access to the information to enhance use by SMEs at local level.*

More in detail also, the following KPI measures performance.

KPI nº	KPI name	KPI target	Success
KPI 2.2	# of thematic communities that are active and on-going by the end of the project	At least 8	Working Groups launched 4 at M6 Others will follow

2 About the Catalogue

2.1 History of the Catalogue

Companies still find difficulties for their digital transformation and this takes time, only one out of five SMEs in the EU are highly digitised, yet they represent over 90% of all businesses in Europe. On top of this, there are strong differences in the level of digitalisation across the EU, depending on the sector and region. The EU proposes Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) as a key priority and tool to support digitalisation².

The Digitising European Industrial (DEI) strategy was launched by the European Commission (EC) in April 2016 as part of the Digital Single Market (DSM) Strategy. DEI aims to reinforce the EU's competitiveness in digital technologies and to ensure that every business in Europe - whichever the sector, wherever the location, whatever the size - can draw the full benefits from digital innovation. Under the DEI initiative, DIHs are seen as “the tool”, a one-stop-shop, to support industry in their digital transformation with knowledge, services and access to technology, testing facilities and different technological and business solutions.

The **Digital Innovation Hubs Catalogue**³ was launched in November 2016 (<http://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/digital-innovation-hubs-tool>). It is part of the implementation of the DEI Strategy, aiming at contributing to the digital transformation of the EU industry. The Catalogue has been coordinated by TNO, in collaboration with other partners, among which TECNALIA⁴ (WP3 leader of DIHNET.EU). The Catalogue has permitted to identify and map more than 500 DIHs in the EU and to provide comprehensive information and characteristics including a description of competencies, services offered and market sectors among others. These DIHs are ecosystems supporting the digitalisation process of SMEs. The Catalogue project of existing DIHs in EU28 Member States provides a comprehensive information to SMEs or industry to find infrastructure and expertise they need and contact to potential partners; a platform to Competence Centres and DIHs to advertise their expertise to potential customers and showcase their activities; policymakers with information about state of play of EU DIHs as well as the identification of networks in the field of digitalisation in the industry.

Initially, it was agreed with the EC to identify DIHs in the different Member States following three minimum conditions:

1. Initiated under on **national policy initiative** to digitize the industry (listed on <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/content/digitising-european-industry-catalogue-initiatives>).
2. **Governmental funding** (private DIHs will be excluded).
3. **3 examples of services available** (in case operational DIHs do not provide the 3 examples the DIH will classified as candidate).

² <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/digital-innovation-hubs>

³ Ref: SMART 2016/0002

⁴ Other partners: Civitta, CPI, D'Appalonia, EDATER, European Dynamics, Jennifer Harper, LIST, SmartIS City, TC CAS, VDI, VTT, University of Zagreb.

On this basis, DIHs submitted a questionnaire that was individually evaluated by the project partners of the DIH Catalogue and those accomplishing the conditions were further included in the Database. DIHs, were thus classified on different maturity levels (fully operational, candidate, in preparation). The Catalogue project was ended by November 2017. The information from the Catalogue was made public and mapped by the Joint Research Centre (JRC). During 2018, the map has been updated and the DIHs assessed by JRC to ensure the quality of the information given. The DIHs were assessed against the following four criteria established by the EC:

1. Be part of a **regional, national or European policy initiative** to digitise industry.
2. Be a **non-profit organisation**.
3. Have a **physical presence in the region and present an updated website** explaining the DIHs' activities and services provided for the digital transformation of SMEs/Midcaps or industrial sectors currently insufficiently taking up digital technologies.
4. Have at least **3 examples of how the DIH has helped a company** with its digital transformation referring to publicly available information, identifying for each: Client profile, Client need, provided solution to meet the need.

During this review, the maturity of DIHs was simplified to two levels fully operational (FO) and in preparation (IP), therefore the candidate condition was included under the preparation one.

Nowadays, the Catalogue compiles 486 DIHs⁵; 266 DIHs published as fully operational; 220 DIHs published as in preparation. Nevertheless, the Catalogue intends to be an "alive" instrument, so that new DIH candidates can get in and complete the request to become DIH and be incorporated in the Catalogue.

The **Catalogue is a good platform for DIHs to network**. On this behalf, the search can be organised by: country, evolutionary stage (now two stages: in preparation, fully operational), technical competencies, services provided, focus on TRL and market sectors). But it is very important that the information that the Catalogue provides it is updated and useful for the users. Nowadays, the last assessment of the Catalogue was finalised by January 2019 by JRC a full assessment was provided including the following aspects⁶:

- A brief presentation of the policy context around the policy indicatives.
- The data base, data collection system of the Catalogue and the assessment methodology followed, the country fiches for 28 EU Member States and 10 Non-EU countries (with information in each case on the policy national and regional initiatives for digitising industry, on the FO and IP DIHs and on the hubs' participation on EU, national or regional projects).
- An analysis on several technology areas, market sectors, provided service examples etc. is presented under this chapter for selected FO DIH cases.
- Conclusions, recommendations and next steps.

The Catalogue is a **very new tool for DIHs and policy makers**, so that so that automatization of the process would be required for the sustainability of the process make it leaner and allow its full potential as a Map-based search tool.

⁵ Data from 17/04/2019.

⁶ Guidelines from the EC 04-february 2019.

2.2 Other relevant initiatives

The EC has launched several initiatives to support the collaboration of DIHs to create an EU-wide network, where companies can access competences and facilities not available in the DIHs of their region⁷. According to the EC, it is expected that this network will lead to knowledge transfer between regions and will be the basis for economies of scale and investments in the DIHs.

Several EU initiatives and projects are supporting this pan-European network of DIHs, where it is expected that DIHNET.EU, this Coordination and Support Action (CSA) will coordinate the whole network of DIHs. The followings projects can be highlighted:

- **I4MS**-ICT Innovation for Manufacturing SMEs (<https://i4ms.eu/>)
- **SAE**-Smart Anything Everywhere (<https://smartanythingeverywhere.eu/>)
- **EIT Digital** (from the European Institute of Innovation and Technology) (<https://www.eitdigital.eu/>) will also contribute to the network of DIHs through its project MIDIH (<http://midih.eu/project.php>).
- **Open Data:**
 - Data Pitch Innovation Programme (<https://datapitch.eu/>)
 - ODINE-Open Data Incubator Europe (<https://opendataincubator.eu/>)
- **Robotics:**
 - ECHORD++-European Coordination Hub for Open Robotics Development (<http://echord.eu/>)
 - ROBOT-NET (<https://robott-net.eu/>)
 - CSA-RODINE-Robotics Digital Innovation Network (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/218635/factsheet/en>).
- **Photonics:**
 - ACTPHAST 4.0-Access Centre for Photonics Innovation Solutions and Technology Support (<http://www.actphast.eu/>)
 - EPRISE- Empowering Photonics through Regional Innovation Strategies in Europe (<https://eprise.eu/>)
- **HPC:**
 - SESAME NET- Supercomputing Exercise for SMEs (<https://sesamenet.eu/>)

To ensure the presence of a DIH in every region by 2020, as some are the EC has launched the following training programmes for new DIHs:

- **I4MS** mentoring programme (<https://i4ms.eu/mentoring-programme>)
- **Smart Factories in new Member States:** training for DIHs in Central and Eastern Europe (training materials also open for consultation)
- **DIHELP** - DIH Enhanced-Learning Programme (<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/dihelp-call-30-digital-innovation-hubs-take-part-training-programme>)
- **EIT Digital** (<https://www.eitdigital.eu/>)

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/digital-innovation-hubs>

On top of these mentioned projects, the Smart Specialisation platform as a "yellow pages" of Digital Innovation Hubs. <http://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/digital-innovation-hubs-tool->

Another relevant network to be considered such as:

- **DG RTD- EPPN network:** European Network for Pilot Production Facilities and Innovation Hubs (<https://www.eppnetwork.com/>)
DG GROW-EU Mapping of Technology Centres in Key Enabling Technologies (KETs)
(<https://www.clustercollaboration.eu/news/eu-mapping-technology-centres-key-enabling-technologies-kets>)

3 Purpose of the Catalogue: Strengths and Weaknesses

3.1 What is the purpose of the Catalogue?

The Catalogue is a platform for DIHs to network and cooperate, acceding competencies and facilities that might not be available at regional level; to transfer knowledge and the basis for economies of scale and investments in the DIH. In practical terms the Catalogue provides:

- A “**yellow page** of DIHs”;
- **Fact-sheets** with profile, contact data, service examples for regional, national, and EU-supported DIHs and
- **Map-based search tool** by technical competences, market sector, services.

3.2 Potential user groups

The Catalogue could have several user groups that might potentially demand as well as offer different services from and for DIHs, among them the followings could be highlighted in table 1:

Table 1: Potential User groups for the Catalogue: preliminary overview of demand and offer of services

User groups	Demand/use from Catalogue	Offer to Catalogue
Companies, SMEs, start-ups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for developing technologies, testing facilities, connections. • Solutions to technological gaps and company demands. 	Challenges to be solved (main clients)
Research Organisations	Networks, connections for better technological developments.	technologies and technological solutions, testing facilities.
Regional Governments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall view of what DIHs offer at regional, national and EU level and where it is available. • Where the needs for digitalisation development are at regional level. • Ecosystem orchestration. • Awareness and dissemination of DIHs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the creation/reinforcement of DIHs that support their regional digitalisation strategy, securing the necessary financial means. • alignment of different initiatives. • export opportunities for regional suppliers (research and products) to other regions.
National Ministries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall view of what DIHs offer at national, regional and EU level and where it is available, where the needs for digitalisation development are. • DIHs per country, focalisation, state of Development. • Strengthened cooperation with other national initiatives and networks. • Awareness and dissemination. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the creation/reinforcement of DIHs that support their national digitalisation strategy, securing the necessary financial means. • Ensure alignment of different initiatives.
EC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall view of what DIHs offer at national, regional and EU level and where it is available, where the needs for digitalisation development are. • Support the creation of the pan-European network. • Strengthened cooperation with other EU-funded projects and networks. • Capacity building programmes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the DIHs and the creation of a pan-EU network of DIHs • Pan-European access to specific innovations and infrastructures by SMEs can be improved; • Alignment and synchronization of development of new capacities on EU-level, increasing efficiency of public funds (Smart Specialisation)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combining pan-EU complementary expertise in developing innovative solutions.
Innovation ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Networking; getting connected at regional, national and EU level. Learning from others. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get connected for better organisation of services to offer. Learn from each other.
DIHs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Networking, catalogue of services/technologies related to specific demands in other EU regions. Reinforce the collaboration activities and capacities Training Learning from different DIHs on how to organise and operate their work 	Information and contacts
Investors	Opportunities for launching new technologies, products	

Source: Own elaboration, TECNALIA

For this purpose, the Catalogue needs to be a high-quality repository of information of DIHs, validated the policy makers of each EU Member State.

3.3 SWOT analysis of the actual Catalogue

The SWOT analysis and matrix is considered as a strategic instrument used to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. It is a good tool to understand, based on the real situation, which are the actions that would need to be launched in the near future to overcome the weaknesses and reinforce the strengths. The analysis of the Strengths and Weaknesses is from an internal perspective, whilst the opportunities and threats for an external one. The idea of incorporating this kind of analysis to the Catalogue is to have a better understanding on what is working well and what will be recommended to be improved, on this basis have evidence for the upgrade of the Catalogue. The following matrix presents the SWOT analysis of the Catalogue, based on the experience of the team in the field, as well as the assessment work of DIHs being carried out.

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unique “yellow pages” gathering most of the DIHs together at EU level. Unique central point to know about each other. Strategic tool for policy making, as key information can be found on DIHs from own country and other countries. Map-based search tool by technical competences, market sector, services. The Catalogue is a very good tool to help DIHs in the networking process. It is a means for DIHs to communicate their expertise to potential customers by showcasing their services on a European level therefore, it set the basis for further collaboration opportunities. 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not a very user- oriented tool so how to know if it is useful for potential user-groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which are the real user groups? Which are the actual demands? Difficult to get the Catalogue sustainable and updated. It is an <i>alive project</i>, that requires from updates according to new digitalisation challenges. Data collection is not lean and mean. The Catalogue has currently self-reported data. Lack of consistent, comprehensive and coherent approach for a productive RIS3-DIH interaction. Difficult to know about the evolution/degree of Maturity of the DIHs from the Catalogue after some time. Connection among DIHs, Smart Specialisation and other existing initiatives at national and regional level supporting digitalisation and networks.
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Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibilities to know about each other. The Catalogue is a platform for DIHs to get to know each other's and further cooperate, acceding competencies and facilities that might not be available at regional/national level. • The DIHNET.EU Community as a perfect complement to animate the Catalogue. • Support local/regional SMEs to find their needs and solve their concerns at EU level. • A "label" could contribute to the accuracy of the data reported in the JRC Catalogue. • DIHs can be important partners for strategy development and feedback for RIS3 processes, sourcing industry needs and Knowledge into RIS3. • Industry 4.0 and DIHs are currently fashionable concepts, the DIHs should try to benefit from the current buzz to engage with potential beneficiaries. • Cross-clustering/cross sectorial innovation for companies, internationalization and competence development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability is not static as it develops with the increasing market and industry requirements and DIHs need to adapt. • Governance of DIHs is heterogeneous for the long-term sustainability and success of these organisations they difference need to be acknowledged and built upon. • Cross-border cooperation as for different rules and regulations. • Difficulties to find solutions to technological problems outside the country and make them possible.

4 DIHNET approach to upgrade the Catalogue

The **Catalogue** is a very good tool to **help DIHs in the networking process**. It is a means for DIHs to communicate their expertise to potential customers by showcasing their services on a European level therefore, it set the basis for further collaboration opportunities.

DIHNET.EU aims to **upgrade and update of the information provided by the Catalogue**. DIHNET.EU already suggested the following steps in the proposal for Task 3. 1. The following table shows the activities and the actions carried out in the project:

Activities planned under Task 3.1	Activities in place and findings
<p>Analysis and update of the information from the Catalogue to provide a landscape of EU DIHs. Our experience shows that the concept of DIHs has raised enormous attention and has exceeded the initial expectative in terms of numbers of DIHs. After the first mapping, all DIHs from the Catalogue have been assessed against updated criteria. But the concept of DIH is still not fully understood, therefore, some entry criteria to assess and quality check the potential DIHs would be suggested together with other networks and relevant stakeholders.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessment of new DIHs and edited versions from the Catalogue against the 4 criteria. A DIH maturity Tool to identify Champions is being developed. The Community supports DIHs to better understand the concepts and better connect. Quality check for DIHs under the Catalogue after certain period needed.
<p>A monitoring tool will be provided to assess their performance within the Catalogue.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The DIH Maturity tool will assess DIHs performance and suggest Champions. An additional monitoring tool will be needed for the DIHs part of the Catalogue after some period e.g. after 1 year of operation.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification of new specifications or functionalities needed to ensure future cooperation towards the creation of a sustainable network. A set of common structures will be defined to ensure a Pan-European collaboration for SMEs as well as for policy makers. To align actions, a systematic multi-user data model e.g. policymakers, SMEs/MidCaps, regional development agencies, individual DIHs, H2020 Innovation Actions, H2020 CSAs could be used. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Community ensures this as well as the Working Groups.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The organisation of the information collection will be ensured with other stakeholders and Community DIHs to support the access to relevant and updated data. Coordination will be ensured with the matchmaking tool described in WP2 task 2.1. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Community ensures this as well as the Working Groups.

Task 3.2 and Task 3.3 also foreseen under WP3 are also producing inputs for Task 3.1. More in detail, these tasks will aim at:

- Task 3.2- From the Catalogue to the DIH Community.** The Catalogue needs to be an alive instrument that offers the information needed for DIHs as well as for the potential users (EU, regional and national governments, DIHs, SMES, mid-caps, entrepreneurs, etc.) to improve collaboration and ensure the networking among them. This task aims at identifying the DIH

Community and contribute to its coordination with the main aim of creating an active, dynamic and coordinated network of specialised DIHs, where the DIHs and related stakeholders create strong links for interacting. For this purpose, the DIH Community will be identified as well as their needs. Further Community planning and alignment is foreseen in coherence with regional, national and EU policies.

- **Task 3.3- Common approach for Maturity Assessment:** A DIH Maturity Tool will be defined and hosted at the DIHNET Community, where **Good Practices**/DIH Champions will be identified and supported as a learning case and tool for others to exchange experiences.

The work under the Catalogue is also in relation to WP1, especially task 1.4: **Activating the DIH Community** where the Action Plan for the Working Groups 1.1 has been delivered in M6. WP2, especially Task 2.4 where the DIH **Maturity assessment tool**. But all in all, all tasks and activities planned under DIHNET.EU will be connected to increase final impact and outcomes as shown in the following figure:

The Catalogue is thus, a cornerstone for DIHNET.EU to link DIHs and make them cooperate. The following chart was shown in the DIH Workshop in Brussels, last 3rd of April 2019 by TECNALIA and represents the work being done.

Some activities to upgrade the Catalogue are already in place, mainly related to:

- the **assessment of individual DIHs candidatures** to be part of the Catalogue against the following four conditions:

- by means of the **DIHNET.EU Community**, which is the perfect complement to the Catalogue and the platform where DIHs can cooperate, connect, get relevant info, etc. Based on this, we have already launched some initiatives such as:
 - Specific Guidelines under the Community to support DIHs while filling their applications under JRC, as the assessment shows that many DIHs do not fully understand how to fill in the information requested. See Annex2.
 - Launched different news related to DIHs and the Catalogue
 - Identify the topics to launch the Working Groups
 - Organise a session with Q&A for the Catalogue that will take place on 3rd May.

Learn how to present your DIH profile in the JRC Catalogue

Q&A with Ms. Begoña Sánchez from Tecnalia

DIHNET.EU Community
May 3rd 12PM CEST

MAY 03

How to present your DIH profile in the JRC Catalogue: Q&A - Begoña Sánchez

by FundingBox

Free

[Register](#)

Description

Don't miss the DIHNET.EU Community Q&A with **Ms. Begoña Sánchez** from Tecnalia, where we will provide tips on how to successfully update your DIH profile in the JRC catalogue!

Date And Time

Fri, May 3, 2019
12:00 PM - 12:45 PM CEST
[Add to Calendar](#)

- Many others are planned and will come soon.

5 Top ten Guidelines to upgrade the Catalogue

We suggest a top-ten list of main Guidelines to upgrade the Catalogue, some of these are already in place, as last 3rd April, we launched the Community in Brussels under the event **6th Working Group of DIHs the DIHNET.EU community platform for DIHs**. We also had the opportunity to get feedback from the audience on the topics to launch the Working Groups that will be active under the Community. Other are suggested to be put in place. In any case, the project is on its 6th month of implementation, so more learning will come and probably more guidance.

In general terms, the Catalogue shows very different stages of evolution concerning DIHs. Some Member States are just beginning to transform their technological infrastructures to full business-oriented initiatives. Others are already evolving into regional “doorways to SMEs”; fully developed ecosystems to support the industry with their implementation of the innovative opportunities of digitisation. At EU level, many ecosystems are created to support the pan-European collaboration, from the H2020 Innovation actions and Coordination Support Actions, to specific Preparatory actions and other initiatives. Collaboration at pan-European level is essential to for the success of the Digital Single Market (DSM) and Digitising European Industry Strategy (DEI).

Consequently, regional, national and European policy is required to support and stimulate the DIHs to create a vibrant European collaborative DIH Network that enables using the benefits from existing European capacities and expertise to enhance the European industry and innovation system at large. Ensuring coordination, connection and coherence of these initiatives is needed for higher and better impacts.

5.1 Creating the DIHNET.EU Community as the interactive community of the JRC Catalogue

The [DIHNET.EU Community](#) is complementary to the JRC DIH catalogue and allows DIHs to meet, exchange, discuss and identify which of their missing expertise can be found in other DIHs across the EU. It is the interactive community of the JRC Catalogue.

The DIHNET.EU project launched the **3rd of April** during the **6th Working Group of DIHs the DIHNET.EU community platform for DIHs**.

DIHNET.EU project will enable the coordination of European, national and regional initiatives directly supporting the digital transformation and DIHs. It will create a sustainable pan-European network of networks, with a focus on regional DIHs, by developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different DIH networks, DIHs and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe.

5.2 Activating the DIHNET.EU Community

The Community upgrades the Catalogue as it is the perfect platform for DIHs to connect, learn, solve their concerns, work together, etc. On top of this, the Community is also the perfect space to get information that will create evidence on the needs for improvement. The following table show part of the activities that we are launching at the DIHNET.EU Community that complement and upgrade the Catalogue.

Evidence-base information:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •News & articles on DIHs
Consultation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Q&A days to answer you specific requests •consultations to understand DIHs concerns and opinions
Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Sharing views •Learn from others •Training
Assessment of new DIH applications and updated ones for the DIH Catalogue:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Guidelines on how to prepare your DIH applications; on when a DIH is FO or IP, etc.
Activating the DIH Community:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Launching Working Groups
DIH Maturity- DIH Champions prize	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Select best practices
Activities to cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Matchmaking •Aligement & synchronisation

5.3 Targeted consultations to understand potential needs for the upgrade

The idea is to propose suggestions for updating and upgrading the Catalogue that are in line with the demand and at the same time coherent with other initiatives already in place, not only from Member States, but also from other networks, Innovative actions, projects, etc. involving DIHs. Information could come from **specific interviews** with target groups and from **consultation** that will be launched in the Community. More in detail, the following actions are planned:

- Selection of a **strategic and limited group of actors to be interviewed** (Member states, DIHs, Regional Development agencies coordinating DIHs, Innovative Actions relevant for the Project, DIH networks, JRC, EC, etc.)
- Agreeing on a **brief set of questions** (including general status of DIHs, real needs for sustainability, cooperation mechanisms -internal and external, regional, national, EU oriented-, cooperation needs, networks in which they are taking part, strategy for getting customers, Digitalisation degree, etc. (see annex 1 for proposal for questions).
- Getting **connected to innovation actions** and other strategic EU projects and initiatives that group DIHs, as they are a key entry point to understand the DIH needs.
- Publish on the DIHNET.EU Community the questions to get further answers from DIHs.

The results from this consultation will be drafted and published at the Community.

5.4 Launch of the Working Groups, keeping them active and connected with other Smart Specialisation related initiatives

The topics for the Working Groups were launched last 3rd of April in Brussels, resulting from an interactive process with the audience using the sli.do inquiry. The following topics were selected to launch them (by order of preference):

1. Finance and funding opportunities, 60%
2. Collaboration activities and mechanisms, 59%
3. Connection with regional and national policies and strategies, 57%
4. Business Models and Sustainability, 56%

These Working Groups are expected to gather DIHs with the aim to solve concerns and propose actions to enhance the topics. They will follow a topic-oriented and outcome-oriented approach. These Working Groups can generate important information and recommendations for policy makers, therefore, we will need to ensure connection to the Smart Specialisation platform and other existing initiatives at national, regional and European level. A consistent, comprehensive and coherent approach for a productive Smart Specialisation-DIH interaction is needed and the Working Groups are a means for it.

5.5 DIHs from the Catalogue need to be monitored

The Catalogue needs to provide high-level quality of data. So far, the data is self-reported by the applicants and assessed before being published against four criteria:

1. Be part of a regional, national or [European policy initiative](#) to digitise the industry.
2. Be a non-profit organisation.
3. Have a physical presence in the region and present an updated website clearly explaining the DIHs' activities and services provided related to the digital transformation of SMEs/Midcaps or industrial sectors currently insufficiently taking up digital technologies.
4. Have at least 3 examples of how the hub has helped a company with their digital transformation, referring to publicly available information, identifying and clearly presenting for each:
 - a. Client profile

- b. Client needs
- c. Provided solution to meet the needs

On top of this, once published we need to ensure a **follow up after some time** according to digitalisation challenges or additional requirements.

KPIs need to be established for the monitoring and evaluation of all DIHs from the Catalogue to assess their impact, the provision of services, their contribution to the regional competitiveness, their connectivity, the digitalisation challenges that they manage to solve, etc. to mention some. The update and upgrade of their profiles would be needed after some time, e.g. after one year. Alignment with national and regional strategies will also need to be ensured.

The conditions to be part of the Catalogue will also probably need to be revised as well as the process to update the information from the Catalogue (leaner, standardised, etc.)

5.6 A Maturity Assessment for DIHs is needed

DIHs Maturity will be assessed against a DIH maturity questionnaire linked to KPIs that will allow to select the DIH Champions. The Procedure will be documented and explained in our DIHNET.EU Community. This will be linked to an “award”.

Our intention is that this Maturity Questionnaire would be available at the DIHNET.EU Community, so any DIH that is part of the Community can have access and self-assess itself to have a preliminary idea on their maturity at any time. In any case, this does not mean that those DIHs that have pre-assessed themselves will be directly selected for the prize. A specific Call will be launched for it.

The learning out from this questionnaire will give important inputs on which actions might be potentially needed to keep the Catalogue upgraded, and specially it will provide guidance for the DIHs that are part of the Catalogue and will need specific update.

5.7 Visibility of Good Practices/DIH Champions

The main purpose is to show success stories on **Mature DIHs/Champions** that can inspire and guide other DIHs in their developments. The announcement and submission of the DIH Champion Challenge will be on the DIHNET.EU Community and the winner will be presented in one of the European Commission events related to Digital Transformation, like the Stakeholders Forum of DIH Annual Event and will be supported from DIHNET.EU.

These experiences can be also visually presented (e.g. short videos), in exhibitions, as they are a good learning for others and could serve for the exchange of experiences.

5.8 Ensuring Coordination/connection and coherence among DIHs and DIH networks

Coordination and connection among the on-going activities for DIHs will be needed. A first step is already mapping of the projects and initiatives that are in line and support DIHs. Once mapped they will be available in the Community and DIHs will be invited to learn more and connect. The same exercise would be also recommendable to be done at national level, especially to ensure alignment with Smart Specialisation strategies as well as digitalisation strategies.

5.9 Continuous feeding Community-Catalogue

As already explained, the Community it is expected to provide high-quality and relevant data, evidence and insights that will be translated in specific suggestions for improvement of the Catalogue as well as for policy makers.

The Catalogue needs to be a tool for Member States, regional governments and policy makers for understanding the state of the play of the nation/regional EU DIHs, and this is not yet the case.

5.10 Additional technical improvements and other updates on the JRC platform

Probably, additional updates might be needed under the JRC platform, but so far, the project team does not have enough information to suggest additional functionalities. This might come after.

Annex 1

Tentative questions to update and upgrade the Catalogue.

1 Do you agree on the actual criteria to consider DIHs in the Catalogue?

- Be part of a regional, national or European policy initiative to digitise industry.
- Be a non-profit organisation.
- Have a physical presence in the region and present an updated website explaining the DIHs' activities and services provided for the digital transformation of SMEs/Midcaps or industrial sectors currently insufficiently taking up digital technologies.
- Have at least 3 examples of how the DIH has helped a company with its digital transformation referring to publicly available information, identifying for each: Client profile, Client need, provided solution to meet the need.

2 If you are a Member State, regional government or policymaker dealing with digitalisation and digital challenges does the Catalogue provide you with information about the state of play of EU DIHs?

3 Do you agree on the actual process to get in the Catalogue when you are a new DIH?

- Getting in the platform and completing the request?
- Or would it be better to have some pre-assessment?

4 Do you think the information presented about DIHs is useful?

- Do they permit your DIH be perfectly advertised on expertise, potential customers and activities?
- Is enough to support any SME or industry to find infrastructure, missing expertise and contact potential partners?
- Do they permit your DIH be better connected?
- Does your DIH have access to a better knowledge on the technological services provided?
- and or expertise?

5 If you are a DIH already on the Catalogue:

- Do you think the information show is enough?
- What info do you miss to better network?
- Does the info shown facilitate the development of networks in the field of digitalization?

6 Once you are already in the Catalogue, do you agree on the process to update your information?

7 Do you think the classification given for DIHs is enough?

- country
- evolutionary stage (now two stages: in preparation, fully operational)
- technical competencies

- services provided
- focus on TRL
- and market sectors
- Do you miss any other chapter?

8 Is the Catalogue offering opportunities to connect to other EU initiatives, networks and projects are supporting this pan-European network of DIHs?

9 Do you think the linkages to Smart Specialisation are clear enough?

10 What are your expectations from the Catalogue? Any suggestion for upgrading it?

11 Do you have any suggestion for the update of the info provided by the Catalogue?

Annex 2

Basic information

1. Name of the person responsible of the DIHs communications:

Not answered yet

2. Email:

Not answered yet

3. Phone number:

Not answered yet

4. Country:

No options selected

5. Region:

Not answered yet

6. Name of DIH. Please try to suggest a unique name that clearly identifies your DIH, and if possible, a short name, self-explanatory.:

Not answered yet

7. Website (in the format <https://...>). Remember it is one of the criteria for a DIH to be published. The website needs to be updated and indicating the DIH's activities and services provided and published in English if possible. Best option is a dedicated website, but at least please provide a specific page describing the DIH.:

Not answered yet

*8. Add Social Media (in the format <https://...>).:

Not answered yet

9. Description (max 3000 characters). Please try to be brief and clear. Present the DIH's activities to support the digital transformation of the SMEs. Indicate

the services provided and the non-for-profit aim of your DIH.:

Not answered yet

Location

*1. Country:

Not answered yet

*2. Zip:

Not answered yet

*3. City:

Not answered yet

*4. Address:

Not answered yet

*5. Regions/ NUTS code information:

Not answered yet

*6. Propose a location in the map:

Not answered yet

Basic Characteristics

*1. Hub type: select Digital Innovation Hub:

Not answered yet

*2. Year of creation:

Not answered yet

3. Technical competences (multiple choice allowed):

No options selected

*3. Technical competences (multiple choice allowed):

Not answered yet

*If you choose "Other" in the question above, please specify::

Not answered yet

4. Geographical scope: in the JRC form you will have to select the scope that better fits the target of your services:

No options selected

5. Services: select the ones offered by you DIHs (multiple choice allowed):

No options selected

*5. Services: select the ones offered by you DIHs (multiple choice allowed):

Not answered yet

*If you choose "Other" in the question above, please specify::

Not answered yet

6. Organisational form: you need to ensure that your DIH is non-profit to be accepted as a DIHs:

No options selected

*6. Organisational form: you need to ensure that your DIH is non-profit to be accepted as a DIHs:

Not answered yet

Specific Characteristics

*1. Number of employees:

No options selected

*2. Number of customers:

No options selected

*3. Type of customers:

No options selected

*4. Turnover:

No options selected

*5. Focus on TRL:

No options selected

6. Market sectors:

No options selected

*6. Market sectors:

Not answered yet

7. Funding type:

No options selected

*7. Funding type:

Not answered yet

*If you choose "Other" in the question above, please specify::

Not answered yet

Evolutionary Stage

*1. Please select between Fully Operational and In preparation following the criteria specified above:

No options selected

Services

1. Description of the service related to technology and link to regional, national and European strategies:

Not answered yet

2. Description of the service related to business models and link to regional, national and European strategies:

Not answered yet

3. Description of the service related to ecosystem building and link to regional, national and European strategies:

Not answered yet

Client profile:

Not answered yet

Client needs:

Not answered yet

Provided solution to meet the needs:

Not answered yet

Client profile:

Not answered yet

Client needs:

Not answered yet

Provided solution to meet the needs:

Not answered yet

Client profile:

Not answered yet

Client needs:

Not answered yet

Provided solution to meet the needs:

Not answered yet

*1. Description of the service related to technology and link to regional, national and European strategies:

Not answered yet

*2. Description of the service related to business models and link to regional, national and European strategies:

Not answered yet

*3. Description of the service related to ecosystem building and link to regional, national and European strategies:

Not answered yet

Strategies

1. Regional: mention the RIS3 strategies that your hub's activities are aligned with:

Not answered yet

2. National: mention the national strategies that your DIH is aligned with:

Not answered yet

3. European: mention the national strategies that your DIH is aligned with:

Not answered yet

4. Mention any EU funded projects and initiatives that you have taken part in (H2020, FP7, I4MS, SAE, big data, robotics, photonics, etc.):

No options selected

*If you choose "Other" in the question above, please specify::

Not answered yet

Coordinator and Partners.

*1. Provide a good mix of RTOs, universities, big companies, SMEs, start-ups, governmental bodies, industry associations etc. that you are cooperating with:

Not answered yet

Processing of personal data

I confirm that I read and understood the information concerning processing of the personal data provided above::

No options selected

*info_clause:

Not answered yet